

Analysis on the Implementation of Lifestyle Audits in the South African Public Service: The Bullying and Rhetoric

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This study seeks to analyse lifestyle audits implementation in the South African public sector. The impact of the scourge of unethical conduct such as corruption in the public service has forced governments around the world to institute proactive and preventative measures to curb the endemic. The study employs a constructivist paradigm that uses a qualitative research approach, which analyses extensive literature sources and official documents on lifestyle audits as well as corruption in the public service. The manuscript is descriptive and analytical in nature as it explores the strides that the government has made, critical considerations, the challenges and proposes nuanced strategies for effective execution. This study highlights that the implementation of lifestyle audits requires massive resource augmentation, there is a lack of political support, and there is a misalignment between the regulatory framework and the constitutional imperative. The study concludes there is a need for capacity building, review of the statutory frameworks and alignment of the legal mandates with the Bill of Rights. Moreover, the study holds that there is a strong need to avoid superficial results and to invest in strengthening the moral fibre. The manuscript will be a springboard for other scholars as it will form a basis of point of reference, influence policy direction in uprooting corrupt practices in the government circles, as well as provide the much-required insight for departments in the public service in the implementation of lifestyle audits.

Keywords: Analysis, lifestyle audit, corruption, public service

Corruption by virtue of its intractable nature has become a universal phenomenon, which Ochieng and Kamau (2021) regard as a contagious disease. It has been identified as one of the challenges confronting the Sustainable Development Goals (Shiyanyo & Ngumbi, 2020). Transparency International (2021) highlights that most countries are failing to stop corruption, and the trend has been on a downward spiral since 2012. The National Anti-Corruption Strategy 2020-2030 indicates that corruption manifests itself in all spheres of society in South Africa. The above has led many governments around the world to continuously seek mechanisms to reduce rampant corruption (Thiankolu, 2018) with lifestyle audits among the deployed strategies.

Mugola (2018) avers that lifestyle audits are relatively new in the government accountability ecosystem. The government of South Africa introduced the phenomenon of lifestyle audits for public servants in 2021. The Guide to Implement Lifestyle Audits in the Public Service (2021) considers lifestyle audit as a strategic intervention that seeks to reset the moral compass. Phakathi (2019) reports that Mr Senzo Mchunu, the former minister of Public Service and Administration, outlined that a lifestyle audit is a barometer that seeks to establish if government employees are living within their means, and it can be used as an accountability instrument for those

that found to have failed the test by unduly benefiting from government opportunities as advocated by Sihanya and Ngumbi (2020).

According to the South African Government News Agency (2023), the President of the Republic of South Africa reports that eleven thousand government employees in the national sphere of government have been subjected to lifestyle audits as of March 2023. Thale (2024) indicates that the Minister in the Presidency, Khumbudzo Ntshavheni, shows that by the end of January 2023, 71 provincial and 24 national departments had reported the completion of their lifestyle audits. The Minister further indicates that by the end of March 2023, there has been an increase in the number of compliant departments, which is thirty-six (36) national government departments and eighty-nine (89) at provincial departments. It is important to indicate that lifestyle audit is not only applicable to South Africa; Transparency International (2021) indicates that there are other countries, such as Kenya, Namibia, Malawi, Nigeria, and Zimbabwe, that are implementing lifestyle audits. Its implementation has not been without challenges. France (2021) posits that although it has been hailed as a panacea for corruption, it has inherent limitations, among them is the fact that it requires a lot of resources (financial & human), which has been a critical factor behind its successful implementation or failure thereto.

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Defining Key Concepts

Defining concepts is critical in giving context to the study, it is on this basis that this section defines the following concepts: analysis, lifestyle audits, corruption and public service.

Analysis: Petrina (2019) regards analysis as a systematic process of breaking a problem into smaller components to gain a comprehensive understanding of its patterns, which is critical for drawing conclusions. Linked to the above assertion, Chambers's Twentieth Century Dictionary (1903) associates the concept with

tracing a phenomenon to its source to unravel its underlying characteristics. From the above, it can be deduced that a lifestyle audit is an intentional phenomenon that seeks to unpack and resolve a particular circumstance.

Lifestyle Audits: Lifestyle audits are gaining traction among scholars, as highlighted by Sihanya and Ngumbi (2020) advocate. Ghai (2018) regards it as a study that seeks to determine whether an individual's lifestyle is commensurate with the disclosed income. Powell (2010) opines that a lifestyle audit is a litmus test that juxtaposes an employee's financial information with their lifestyle, which Coenen, Munjeyi, and Mujuru (2018) regard as suspicious profiling, net worth analysis, and an intelligence background investigation. Those whose living expenses surpass their income are suspected of funding their lifestyle through illicit means, as argued by various scholars (Munjeyi & Mujuru, 2018; Powell, 2010; Thompson, 2020).

Corruption: Corruption is behavior that deviates from the normal duties of a public role because of private-regarding (family, close private clique), pecuniary or status gains (Nye, 1967). Philip (2002) similarly emphasizes that corruption is at the centre of the growing trust deficit between government and the public. This concept resonates well with the study's focus, as lifestyle audits are among the government's proactive interventions to curb corruption.

Public Service: Public service "serves" members of the public through the provision of public goods and services. Spicker (2009) outlines, amongst others, the following activities provided by the public service: policing, public health, housing, and education. Shittu (2020) opines that public service is funded through taxes and that its use must be subject to an accountability test. In the South African context, public service refers to national and provincial government departments' employees as outlined in the Public Service Act, 1994 (Proclamation 103 of 1994), and the Public Service Regulations (Mafunisa, 2003).

The discussion above provides some dots linking the three concepts and their relevance to this study. Firstly, analysis enabled researchers to provide a comprehensive understanding of lifestyle audits, including their implications on service delivery machinery. Secondly, corruption has dire implications for service delivery, as perpetrators divert public resources intended for the public good for their personal gain. Brown (2019) argues that a lifestyle audit is about suspicious consumption patterns that manifest in the way a government employee incurs personal expenses to maintain a specific lifestyle. Lifestyle audits are tools used by the government as an early warning sign for employees living beyond their salaries (Powell, 2010). Sihanya and Ngumbi (2020) argue that such a pattern suggests that money is coming from somewhere and can be a basis for investigation. McIntyre and De Villiers (2020) posit that at the centre of the lifestyle audit are bank statement assessments, integrity assessments on the extent of assets declarations, and field observation. It is the researchers' view that money coming from illegal or unexplained sources could point towards an official trapped in a conflict of interest or potentially participating in illicit activities using the public purse. Mbele (2023) regards a lifestyle audit as an exercise that measures legitimate income against a person's lifestyle.

Constitutional and Legal Frameworks Underpinning Lifestyle Audits in South Africa

The South African lifestyle audits regime is embedded in existing

anti-corruption frameworks, as in many other countries, such as Kenya (Chieng & Kamau, 2021). This implies that to locate its legal basis for implementation, a reflection has to be made on sections of various statutes and policy documents for combating corruption.

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996

Public administration is undergirded by the ideals and principles outlined in the Republic of South Africa's Constitution, 1996. Included in these are principles that may be unique to public services, such as impartiality, loyalty, neutrality, accountability, transparency, and diligence (Public Service Commission, 2021). Section 195(1) of the Constitution, 1996 prescribes nine basic tenets which underscore public administration in South Africa. It is an embodiment of what members of society expect from all public servants.

Public Service Act, 1994 (Proclamation 103 of 1994)

The Public Service Act (Proclamation 103 of 1994) and its regulations allow for lifestyle audits in the public service (Kamur, 2021). Section 3(1) (h) of the Act states that "*The minister is responsible for establishing norms and standards relating to integrity, ethics, conduct and anti-corruption in the public service*" (Public Service Act, 1994). Linking to the above assertions by Kamur (2021) it is important to indicate that the Act is not explicitly talking about lifestyle, however, one can deduce that read together with the Guide to Implement Lifestyle Audit in the Public Service (2021) issued by the DPSA, it becomes substantial ground for the government to introduce lifestyle audits. Echoing the same assertion is the expression by McIntyre and Aslett (2022) who posit that the implementation of the lifestyle audits could be linked to the Public Service Act by virtue of understanding that a lifestyle audit is one of the acceptable fraud prevention and detection mechanisms.

Public Service Regulations, 2016

Public Service Regulations (2016) sets section 195 of the Constitution, 1996 in motion, given the fact that it is a lever that enabled the government to introduce mechanisms to enhance ethics within public administration and also to put systems in place to curb corruption. The Act designates a head of department as the driver in the quest for fighting corruption. Section 22(c) provides that "a head of department shall develop and implement an ethics management strategy that prevents and deters unethical conduct and acts of corruption". The Guide to Implement Lifestyle Audits in the Public Service (2021) states that the mandate of departments to conduct lifestyle audits is established by this Act. It is, however, important to indicate that the Act is not explicit about lifestyle audits, as such arriving at this conclusion is a product of drawing inferences.

Public Administration Management Act, 2014 (Act 11 of 2014)

This Act concretises the government's position in its efforts to deal with corruption. It sets section 195(1) of the Constitution in motion as it is premised on curbing unethical practices in public administration. It is important to indicate that this Act, similar to Public Service Regulations (2016) does not talk about lifestyle audits, however, by its objects stipulated in section 3, one could deduce that this Act can also be used as a basis to implement lifestyle audits in South Africa.

Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA), 2013 (Act 4 of 2013)

According to de Bruyn (2014), the POPI legislation defines personal data as that information which enables the user to link it with a particular person, such as race, marital status, health, gender, sex, pregnancy, ethnic origin, religion, disability, belief, as well as any identifying number or symbol, like an e-mail address, physical address, telephone number or online identifier. Berry (2014) posits that the POPIA introduces a new regime on how institutions collect, store, use, and share personal information. The definition above throws a critical spanner in the works for persons and institutions responsible for lifestyle audits, as highlighted by Powell and Roux (2023). This study opines that disregard of the provisions of this Act might result in protracted litigation, which would be an undesirable consequence of lifestyle audits.

Theoretical Framework on Lifestyle Audits

There are several theories used by scholars to provide the theoretical underpinnings linked to corruption, which include the principal-agent theory, collective action theory, game theory, and institutional theory. This study uses the institutional theory as a point of departure in order to unearth the intricate factors underlying corruption in the public service. Various scholars used this theory to analyse corruption in organisations (Luo, 2002; Pillay & Kluvert, 2014). This study subscribes to the propositions of this theory based on the fact that corruption happens within an institution, as expressed by Sudibyo and Jianfu (2015). It is the researchers' conviction that institutional theory will play a pivotal role in unearthing the intricate factors underpinning corruption in the public service.

Origin of the Theory

Institutional theory was canvassed by Meyer and Rowan (1977) with its roots traceable to Max Weber's seminar writing in the 1950s on legitimacy and authority. This theory is recognised as one of the most prominent perspectives in modern organisational research (David & Bitektine, 2009; Greenwood, Oliver, Sahlin, & Suddaby, 2008). Through it, one can piece together the rationale behind institutions' adoption and spread of formal organisational structures. This includes the policy direction, standard practices, and new forms of organisations (Scott, 2001; David, Tolbert, & Boghssian, 2019).

Principles of the Theory

The principles of institutional theory are derived from the writing of DiMaggio and Powell (1983) in their expression of three mechanisms of isomorphic process. The first one, which is coercive isomorphism, describes organizational change which is attributable to the authority imposed by political decisions. Mimetic isomorphism is the second mechanism, stemming from organisations' failure to set clear goals, which leads them to imitate others. Lastly, normative isomorphism, which holds that changes in organizations and professions result from pressure from the surrounding environment. From the above propositions by DiMaggio and Powell (1983) one can depict a link between institutional theory and corruption, as per the argument by Luo (2002), who paints a clear picture of how corruption becomes an entrenched and institutionalised phenomenon for individuals and organisations. This happens despite the existence of a comprehensive regulatory environment.

Relevance of the Theory to the Study

The constructs of institutional theory cogently provide a theoretical posture that unravels the challenges confronting the government operations in South Africa. It glaringly demonstrates the underlying issues that make it difficult for the government to curb corruption. Linked to the above constructs, Tolbert and Zucker (1996) argue that, given their interests, people would follow what others are doing without questioning. From the above assertion, one can deduce that a corrupt environment can contribute to people's unethical behaviour, as they consider it an acceptable practice. Moreover, the extent of the relevance of institutional theory is articulated in the National Anti-Corruption Strategy (2020-2030) wherein it is indicated that “*corruption manifests in all spheres of society and occurs in the public sector and in the private sector, and it permeated key institutions in both the public and private sector, poses a threat to national security, undermines the rule of law and institutions vital to ensuring the centrality of the state as a protector and promoter of the rights of its citizens*”.

There are several cases in South Africa that have become a point of reference on how corruption has entrenched itself in the public service, and it forms the basis upon which government took a decision to implement lifestyle audits as a strategy to fight the pandemic. Amongst other cases is the revelations contained in the Zondo Commission; the recent revelations by the Secretary General of the African National Congress, as reported by Nkonki (2023) that the African National Congress defended its former president (Jacob Zuma), even going to the highest law-making body (Parliament) to declare a swimming pool as a fire pool.

Genesis of Lifestyle Audits in South Africa

Mbele (2023) argues that the compulsory lifestyle audits were introduced in April 2021 by Ayanda Dlodlo (the former Minister of Public Service & Administration). This was a direct response to the clarion call made by the President of the Republic of South Africa in 2018, who called for lifestyle audits to be conducted on all executive managers in government, including himself, as an initiative to curb corruption in the public sector (South African Government News Agency, 2018). It is the researchers' view that the introduction of lifestyle audits in South Africa could not come as a surprise since it was in tandem with the aspirations of the President in his maiden speech on 21 December 2018. The South African Government News Agency (2017) reported that the President committed that “*Corruption must be fought with the same intensity and purpose that we fight poverty, unemployment and inequality*”. Odeku (2019) regards President Ramaphosa (the President) as an active champion of lifestyle audits, advocating that all public servants be subjected to lifestyle audits.

To spearhead its implementation, a Technical Task Team was established by the President, comprised of the President, and some of the key institutions established to combat corruption which include the Auditor-General, the South African Police Service, the South African Revenue Service, the State Security Agency, the Anti-Corruption Task Team, the Office of the Public Service Commission, and the Financial Intelligence Centre (Sihanyi & Ngumbi, 2020). It is also important to indicate that the introduction cannot be divorced from the pressure from civil society and the media for the government to come up with innovative ways to fight corruption. Odeku (2019) points to the Auditor General's work in putting

pressure on the government to adopt preventive measures to curb corruption. The Auditor General's reports have a detailed footprint of anomalies with regard to the management of public funds, which, if not dealt with effectively, could be a fertile ground for corruption.

Furthermore, the revelations by the Zondo Commission were a glaring confirmation that the need to implement lifestyle audits was not a product of ill-conceived ideation. As alluded to by Powell and Roux (2023) the fact that South Africa continues to experience high levels of corruption, as illustrated in the 2022 Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), is yet another piece of evidence to support the government's reasons for its decision to implement lifestyle audits as part of its control arsenal. Ndlele (2017) argues that expanding the implementation of lifestyle audits to municipalities where corruption is endemic will send a clear message about the government's stance against the scourge of corruption.

From the above expositions, it is clear that the introduction of lifestyle audits in South Africa is a step in the right direction. This assertion is supported by Okoye (2017) who argues that robust measures are urgently required to combat corruption before it engulfs the remaining ethical fibre in the public service.

Benefits of Implementing Lifestyle Audits in the South African Public Service

Effective implementation of lifestyle audits serves as a deterrent to those aspiring to engage in corrupt activities, thereby setting aside their moral and constitutional obligations (Odeku, 2019). Gillespie (2014) regards lifestyle audits as a progressive government intervention and a valuable instrument for detecting fraudulent activities and assessing the extent to which government employees remain true to their income and asset declarations. Furthermore, lifestyle audits, when used effectively, can serve as a microscopic lens that reveals the divisive tactics cronies use to conceal corrupt proceeds under the names of other people (World Bank & United Nations Office on Drugs & Crime 2012). The above is linked to the assertion by France (2021) who opines that a lifestyle audit can serve as solid ground for launching formal investigations. This study cautions that subjecting employees to lifestyle audits does not imply that one is corrupt; rather, it seeks to test their potential.

Mbele (2023) argues that through lifestyle audits, the government can uncover the moral ills confronting its employees, such as unexpected wealth and conflicts of interest. Furthermore, a lifestyle audit is considered a preventive measure against unethical and criminal behaviour (Department of Public Service & Administration, 2021) whereas Niven (2021) asserts that through lifestyle audits, employees are aware that there is an invisible camera hovering over their heads and they may be caught, subsequently having to account for their wealth accumulated illicitly. Knowing that there is a potential for being exposed for abusing state resources, people could feel disincentivised to act outside the confines of the prescripts. As expressed in the Department of Public Service and Administration Report (2021) the implementation of lifestyle audits in the public service as a tool for curbing corruption will ultimately contribute to the government's aspirations of building a developmental and capable state.

Lifestyle audits come in handy to fill the void and reveal employees' dishonest behaviour. This stems from the fact that employers have little information about their employees except access to detailed data about the pay of their staff members. They only get saddened by inexplicable

changes in an employee's lifestyle. This is frequently the only sign of criminal activity which in most cases comes late, since at that time employees may now quickly and easily cover up their fraudulent activities (Simone, 2023). Moreover, lifestyle audits can be a crucial fraud risk indicator (Radcliffe, 2004; Gillespie, 2014) that can help law enforcement agents limit their focus to those who have been proven to be living beyond their means.

Challenges in the Implementation of Lifestyle Audits

Although lifestyle audits are regarded as one of the renowned corruption-busting strategies, it has its own sets of challenges that if not addressed, may thwart its successful implementation. The first illustration of the challenges was depicted in the delays with the commencement of its implementation which Nkanjeni (2023) resulted in the President being taken to task by opposition political parties. Conducting a comprehensive lifestyle audit in the public service is a massive project that requires well-resourced institutions/agencies. France (2021) considers the implementation of lifestyle audits impractical and resource-intensive. Nduvi (2021) opines that the effective implementation of lifestyle audits can be hindered by inadequate resources, resulting in a failure to expedite corruption cases within a reasonable time. Therefore, it is on this basis that the authors deduce that resourcing the agencies responsible for its implementation remains critical.

Its successful implementation is embedded in the existence of a comprehensive regulatory regime. As it stands, in South Africa, there is no specific statute about lifestyle audits except for sections in various laws and policy documents for combating corruption, as alluded to by McIntyre and Aslett (2022). Ochieng and Kamau (2021) regard it as a lack of dedicated law on lifestyle audits and they argue that the lack of a unified legislative framework governing lifestyle audits may stifle government aspirations to fight corruption. Linked to the legal framework is the legal mandate of agencies assigned to conduct lifestyle audits. Cave (2021) argues that there is a need to ensure that the agencies designated to conduct lifestyle audits have the necessary legal mandates. This implies that the assignment of such responsibility must fall within its spatial and functional realm, failure of which may have a negative impact during implementation especially when action or consequence management has to be implemented. It is important to highlight that implementing a complex phenomenon like lifestyle audits through a guide carries implications, given its lack of authority to enforce compliance compared to a statute.

The lack of political will to support its implementation could be another fatal blow. From these assertions, the researchers deduce that it is one thing to make public pronouncements (by political leaders & senior government officials), as well as signing policy guidelines, and it is another thing to sanction the actual investigations, as well as the implementation of consequences management to the affected officials.

Another variable is the alignment between the legal frameworks for lifestyle audits and the Constitution, 1996. This stems from the fact that the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, confers many rights on people; therefore, it remains important that implementers be careful not to trample on people's rights, thereby resulting in costly court battles. Powell and Roux (2023) posit that POPIA has introduced several obligations that have the potential to stall the process through legal contestations.

Corrupt individuals (the majority of them are public servants & policymakers) conceal their money in offshore accounts. Declaring their riches is difficult because the majority of their revenues are hidden in offshore accounts, which are not open to public inspection (Animashau & Chitimura, 2021). Kamur (2021) reiterates that agencies charged with the responsibility of conducting lifestyle audits must understand that lifestyle audits are not conclusive, as such alone cannot provide substantial ground to take action against an employee, otherwise, it may lead to protracted litigations, which have to be avoided at all costs. Echoing the same sentiment is expressed by President Ramaphosa when giving account of the delays in the commencement of the project that it would have led to very superficial results” and a change in the service provider (Nkanjeni, 2023). It can therefore be argued that successful implementation of lifestyle audits requires well-resourced institutions/agencies/units with the requisite skills.

Implementation of Lifestyle Audits in Other African Countries

Lifestyle audits in Kenya can reveal the extent to which government employees are involved in illegal activities, thus laying bare who ate what, who continues to eat, who is likely to eat, and what they like eating (Mutunga, 2021). Ngumbi (2019) indicates that in Kenya, noticeable progress was made in investigating former governors on corruption; however, none of them have been convicted owing to the fact that lifestyle audits fail to generate concrete evidence for effective convictions. According to Daily Monitor (2018), the Uganda Revenue Authority's lifestyle audits were instrumental in the investigation of claims of tax fraud and other illicit activities involving government employees. Similarly, the East African (2020) indicates that the lifestyle audit provided a strong basis for Rwandan Revenue Authority in its investigations and thus reduced tax evasion and prevented further loss of revenue. Animashuanand Chitimira (202) indicate that lifestyle audit in Nigeria could not be effective in curbing corruption due to the failure by the authorities to adopt and integrate technology, and a lack of political will. Animashuanand Chitimira (2022) further apportioned the failure to effectively implement lifestyle audits to the constitutional powers that protect the president, governors, and their deputies from any criminal or civil offence committed whilst in office.

Nduvi (2021) says that although lifestyle audit is firmly rooted in several provisions of Kenya's 2010 Constitution, efforts to reduce corruption in the public sector have been questionable over time. Antwi (2023) opines that Ghana has several laws that should measure the extent of the conduct of public servants, however, such laws are not being implemented. He argues that lifestyle audits will be a strategic intervention that can be used to authenticate the declarations made by public servants, since currently, nobody knows whether such declarations are a true reflection of what they have. The Zimbabwean government experienced the same challenges encountered by Nigeria and Kenya, where the findings of the lifestyle audits were inconclusive and could not be used as a solid basis for prosecution, as highlighted by Munjeji and Mujuri (2018).

Prerequisites for Successful Implementation of Lifestyle Audits in the South African Public Service

For the successful implementation of lifestyle audits in the South African public service, the manuscript proposes the following

prerequisites: -

Capacity Building: There is an urgent need for the government to ensure that agencies designated to conduct lifestyle audits are well-capacitated. This includes both in terms of the number of personnel as well as the quality of personnel. This implies that officials charged with this responsibility must have the requisite skills to enable them to execute their tasks effectively and efficiently.

Statutory Framework: The ultimate end of conducting lifestyle audits is the implementation of consequence management for the affected persons, which can be a subject of legal contestation and litigations. It is therefore important for the government to ensure that the legislative framework regulating the implementation of lifestyle is clear and not subject to legal interpretations.

Legal Mandates: It is important to ensure that agencies designated to conduct lifestyle audits have the necessary mandate. This implies that the assignment of such responsibility must fall within their spatial and functional realm.

Alignment of Lifestyle Audits Frameworks and the Rights of People: The Constitution, 1996 is the supreme law in South Africa, and it protects the rights of people as contained in the Bill of Rights. Therefore, it remains critical to ensure that the endeavour by the government to fight corruption through implementing lifestyle audits does not trample over the rights of people.

Need to Avoid Superficial Results: The implementation of lifestyle audits requires a rigorous exercise with complex legal implications, therefore, its implementation must not be guided by unreasonable timelines. This may result in the release of superficial results that will not assist the process, and may not stand the test of time before the courts of law.

Building Moral Fibre: Without underestimating the importance of the implementation of lifestyle audits, it remains critical for the government to continue implementing interventions that seek to reconstruct the damaged moral fibre of society, which is attributable to the rampant corruption in South Africa.

Conclusion

The South African public service exists to provide services to members of the public. This can only happen if its machinery is effective, efficient, accountable, and responsive. The public officials must abide by minimum mandatory standards, principles, and values. The constitutional framework remains the anchor of the ethical standards expected throughout the public service. Effective implementation of lifestyle audits hinges upon an explicit regulatory framework that provides clarity and guidance during convictions. In this case, Section 195 (1) of the Constitution sets the tone and paints a clear picture of the kind of public service that will be responsive to the desires and expectations of the populace.

To enforce the above values, the Republic of South Africa has introduced lifestyle audits. Various challenges confront the implementation of lifestyle audits. These include, inter alia, delay in its implementation, agencies to implement lifestyle audits not well capacitated, lack of political will to implement the lifestyle audit, and lack of alignment between the legal frameworks for lifestyle audits and the Bill of Rights enshrined in the Constitution. It is concluded that there is an urgent need for the government to ensure that agencies designated to conduct lifestyle audits are well-capacitated and that the endeavour by the government to fight corruption through implementing lifestyle audits does not trample on the rights of people.

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